

INTERFACIAL TENSION AND COMPLEXING TENDENCY OF METAL CHLORIDES AND NITRATES. AUTOCOMPLEX FORMATION AND IONISATION CHANGES IN SALT SOLUTIONS

BY HEMLATA KAZI

Seven complexes are observed in mixed solutions of lead or beryllium chloride and alkali chloride, except lithium chloride with which six complexes are formed, irrespective of change in salt concentration. Beryllium and thorium chloride each forms seven complexes with lead, zinc, calcium, barium, strontium and mercuric chloride and five complexes with cadmium, magnesium, cobalt, copper and nickel chloride in their mixed solutions. Complex formation between silver, alkali, zinc, aluminium, chromium nitrates and alkali nitrates, among cerium, aluminium, chromium nitrates, among trivalent and bivalent nitrates of barium, cadmium, zinc and lead and also between thorium and beryllium nitrates has been examined. Complex-ion formation is evident in the solutions of cobalt, nickel, lead chloride, mercuric chloride and bromide, but not in those of cadmium bromide, zinc and alkaline earth chlorides.

In an earlier communication Desai (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 957) reported the complexing capacity of different cations among metal chlorides excepting those of beryllium and thorium. Beryllium cation, because of its small size and high nuclear charge, and thorium, of its large cation charge, should possess high complexing power in the mixed solutions of other metal salts (cf. Hemlata Kazi, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 763). This investigation was undertaken to study the nature and number of complexes formed between beryllium, lead or thorium chloride and other metal chlorides in their mixed solutions. The tendency of complex formation between alkali nitrates and bivalent nitrates, cerium or thorium nitrate was reported previously (*loc.cit.*). This work further includes such complex formation between monovalent nitrates, zinc, aluminium, chromium and other nitrates.

The colour changes of aqueous cupric chloride on dilution were first attributed to the progressive solvation and then to the formation and dissociation of complex ions (Wiederman, *Brit. Assoc. Rep.*, 1887, p. 364; Donnan and Basset, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 61, 939; Bhagvat, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 52; Yajnik *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 356). Five peaks, obtained by plotting interfacial tension of aqueous cupric chloride against solute concentration, were explained by Desai and Kazi (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 418) on the basis of the formation and dissociation of complex anions due to autocomplexing:

Such interfacial tension measurements were carried out with cobalt and nickel chlorides, which might be expected to show such minima and maxima in interfacial tension values with change in concentration. By means of these measurements, ionisa-

tion changes in solutions of mercuric chloride and bromide, cadmium bromide, lead, barium, strontium, calcium and zinc chlorides were studied with change in concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

The salts used were of standard quality. A solution of salt B (12 c.c.) was taken in a 50 or 100 c.c. flask and different volumes of the solutions of salt A of the same concentration as that of B were added to it and the total volume was made up to 50 or 100 c.c. as the case might be. Thus, a series of mixed solutions was prepared by the *monovariation method from each of the pairs of stock solutions for measuring interfacial tension against n-butyl or isoamyl acetate*. The peaks, obtained by plotting the tension values against the respective volumes of the variant A, indicate complex formation (graphs not shown). The compositions of these complexes are shown in the last column of Tables I-III.

TABLE I

[a = A.4B, b = A.3 B, c = A. 2 B, d = 2 A.3 B, e = A.B, f = 3 A.2B, g = 2 A.B].

Conc. (M/).	Salt A	Salt B.	Complexes.
25	PbCl ₂	KCl or NH ₄ Cl or NaCl	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
30	"	"	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
60	"	"	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
100	"	"	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
25 to 100	"	LiCl	a,-,c,d,e,f,g
2/25	BeCl ₂	KCl or NH ₄ Cl or NaCl	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
100	"	"	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
10	"	"	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
2/25	"	LiCl	a,-,c,d,e,f,g
2	"	"	a,-,c,d,e,f,g
100	"	"	a,-,c,d,e,f,g

TABLE II

[a = A.4 B, b = A.3 B, c = A. 2B, d = A.B, e = 2A.B, f = 3A.B, g = 4A.B].

Conc. (M/).	Salt A.	Salt B.	Peaks corresp. to.	Conc. (M/).	Salt A.	Salt B	Peaks corresp. to:
100	BeCl ₂	PbCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	50-100	NaCl	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
100	"	ZnCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	50-100	NH ₄ Cl	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
80-100	"	CdCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,-	50-100	CdCl ₂	ThCl ₄	-,-,c,d,e,f,g
100	"	MgCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	60-100	MgCl ₂	ThCl ₄	-,-,c,d,e,f,g
50-100	"	HgCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,-	100	ZnCl ₂	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
80-100	"	SrCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	80-100	PbCl ₂	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
80-100	"	CaCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	100	BeCl ₂	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
80-100	"	BaCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	60-100	CuCl ₂	ThCl ₄	-,-,c,d,e,f,g
50-100	"	CoCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,-	90	CuCl ₂	ThCl ₄	-,-,c,d,e,f,g
50-100	"	CuCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,-	80	NiCl ₂	ThCl ₄	-,-,c,d,e,f,g
50-100	"	NiCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,-	100	HgCl ₂	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
2	"	ZnCl ₂	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	50-100	SrCl ₂	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
80-100	LiCl	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	50-100	CaCl ₂	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
50-100	KCl	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g	50-100	BaCl ₂	ThCl ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g

TABLE III

[$a=A.4B$, $b=A.3B$, $c=A.2B$, $d=A.B$, $e=2A.B$, $f=3A.B$, $g=4A.B$]

Conc. (M/),	Salt A.	Salt B.	Peaks correspond to.
30	NaNO ₃	KNO ₃ or LiNO ₃ or NH ₄ NO ₃	d
30	LiNO ₃	KNO ₃ or NH ₄ NO ₃	d
300	KNO ₃	LiNO ₃ or NH ₄ NO ₃	d
300	AgNO ₃	LiNO ₃ or NaNO ₃ or NH ₄ NO ₃	d
20	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	KNO ₃ or NaNO ₃ or NH ₄ NO ₃	a,c,d
100	"	LiNO ₃	a,c,d
20	"	"	c,d
50	Al(NO ₃) ₃	KNO ₃ or NH ₄ NO ₃ or NaNO ₃	a,b,c,d
100	"	LiNO ₃	a,b,c,d
10	"	"	b,d
50	Cr(NO ₃) ₃	KNO ₃ or NH ₄ NO ₃ or NaNO ₃	a,b,c,d
100	"	LiNO ₃	a,b,c,d
10	"	"	b,d
100	Al(NO ₃) ₃	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	a,b,c,d
100	Cr(NO ₃) ₃	"	a,b,c,d
100	"	Al(NO ₃) ₃	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
100	Be(NO ₃) ₂	Th(NO ₃) ₄	a,b,c,d,e,f,g
100	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	c,d,e,f,g
100	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	"	c,d,e,f,g
100	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	"	c,d,e,f,g
100	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	"	c,d,e,f,g
100	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	Al(NO ₃) ₃	c,d,e,f,g

DISCUSSION

Seven complexes (a,b,c,d,e,f,g) are observed for each of the series of mixed salt solutions of lead or beryllium chloride and potassium, sodium or ammonium chloride; while six complexes (a,c,d,e,f,g) are only evident with such solutions of lead or beryllium and lithium chloride (vide Table I). Thus, with lead or beryllium chloride — alkali chloride systems, the number and nature of available complexes do not vary with change in salt concentrations in contrast with such systems of mercuric chloride or bromide, copper or cobalt chloride and alkaline earth chlorides (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 426, 873; 1954, 31, 329, 415).

The formation of seven-complexes (a,b,c,d,e,f,g) is evident between beryllium or thorium chloride and mercuric, lead, zinc, calcium, strontium or barium chloride each in their mixed solutions; while cadmium, magnesium, copper, cobalt or nickel chloride forms only five complexes (a,b,c,d,e) with beryllium chloride and also similar five complexes (c,d,e,f,g) with thorium chloride, only the variant being different in the latter system (vide Table II). It may be pointed out that beryllium nitrate and thorium nitrate each forms with alkali nitrates seven complexes of similar molecular compositions (a,b,c,d,e,f,g; cf. Hemlata Kazi, *loc.cit.*); thorium chloride also forms such seven complexes with alkali chloride, but the seven complexes formed with beryllium chloride are not similar to those formed with thorium chloride — (1) A.4B, (2) A.3B, (3) A.2B, (4) A.3B, (5) A.B, (6) 3 A.2B, (7) 2 A.B. (vide Table I).

The results of metal nitrates indicate that silver and alkali nitrates form only one complex (d) among themselves, while zinc nitrate and nitrates of aluminium and chromium form three (a,c,d) and four (a,b,c,d) complexes respectively with alkali nitrates, except lithium nitrate with which number of complexes formed varies from three to two (c,d) with zinc nitrate, and four to two (b,d) with trivalent nitrates, with change in salt concentration (vide Table III). Aluminium nitrate forms seven complexes (a,b,c,d,e,f,g) with chromium nitrate, but both these nitrates indicate only four complexes (a,b,c,d), when mixed with cerium nitrate. Cerium nitrate shows the formation of four complexes (d,e,f,g) with nitrate of lead, zinc, cadmium or barium. Such a behaviour is also shown by aluminium nitrate when mixed with lead nitrate. Thorium nitrate indicates seven complexes (a,b,c,d,e,f,g) when mixed with beryllium nitrate.

The problem of complexing among different chlorides and nitrates may be related to ion polarisation. When ions approach each other, the attraction of the cation for the electron atmosphere of the anion and the simultaneous repulsion of the nucleus of the anion result in the deformation of the anion. The cation would be similarly polarised by the anion. The complexing tendency will be greater for ions of smaller radius and those of higher valency.

The interfacial tension values of aqueous cobalt and nickel chlorides at different concentrations varying from 1.5 M to $M/100,000$ were measured against *n*-butyl acetate and, when plotted against the concentrations of the solute, show five peaks (Fig. 1) at concentrations 1.2 M, 0.7 M, 0.25 M, 0.008 M and 0.0005 M of cobalt and nickel chlorides. The formation and dissociation of complex anions in cobalt and nickel chloride solutions due to autocomplexing account for the peaks in tension values in a manner analogous to that of cupric chloride (*loc.cit.*).

The tension-concentration curves of lead, mercuric, zinc halides etc., obtained with *isoamyl acetate* (vide Fig. 2), pass through a sharp depression at $0.05 \times 10^{-3} M$ and then rise showing a maximum at $0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ in all cases. Thereafter, there is a decrease in tension with increase in concentration of salts, except lead chloride, mercuric chloride and bromide, which show a second maximum at $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. The curves, obtained with *n*-butyl acetate (not shown), however, indicate the second peak at $7.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, the position of the maximum shifting with different liquids (cf. this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 636).

FIG. 2

The first peak is indicative of the salt ionisation in the following manner :

these ions forming the electrical double layer at the interface. Since only one peak is evident with zinc, alkaline earth halides and cadmium bromide, ionic species, likely to be present in these salt solutions, are M^{2+} , MX^+ and X^- . The second peak, observed with lead and mercuric halides, indicates change in ionisation due to complex-ion formation in the following manner :

Hence, the ions present in extremely dilute solutions of lead and mercuric halides are M^{2+} , MX^+ and X^- , but with increase in salt concentration the complex ions MX_3^- and MX_4^{2-} should be also present along with other ions in solution (cf. this *Journal* 1954, 31, 638) as in the case of cadmium iodide solution in which both CdI_3^- and CdI_4^{2-} are supposed to be present (cf. Riley and Gallafant, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 522).

The author thanks Dr. C. M. Desai for his keen interest in the work and the College authority for facilities.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
M. T. B. COLLEGE, SURAT.

Received September 6, 1954.